

Multi-scale Modelling Of The Textile Composite Materials

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Introduction (DURACOMP)

Multi-scale modelling

Interface elements

RVE material properties

Numerical example

- Predict and describe macroscopic material behaviour by considering the mechanics of the **underlying microstructure**.

- FE^2 , because it requires the simultaneous computation of the mechanical response at two different scale.

- ❑ Definition of macrostructural B.V.P.
- ❑ Definition of a microstructural representative volume element (RVE).
(with known constitutive behaviour of individual constituents)
- ❑ Formulation of the microscopic boundary conditions.
(macro-to-micro transition or localization or downscaling)
- ❑ Solution of microstructural B.V.P.
- ❑ Calculation of the macroscopic output variables.
(micro-to-macro transition or homogenization or upscaling)
- ❑ Numerical relation between the macroscopic input and output variables

- ❑ Linear displacement boundary conditions are used.
- ❑ The micro displacement field

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}^* + \tilde{\mathbf{u}},$$

- ❑ Taylor displacement is written as

$$\mathbf{u}_i^* = \mathbb{D}_i^T \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$\mathbb{D}_i = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 2y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2y_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2y_3 \\ y_2 & y_1 & 0 \\ 0 & y_3 & y_2 \\ y_3 & 0 & y_1 \end{bmatrix}_i$$

- ❑ Finally, the homogenised stress is calculated as

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^{n_b} \mathbb{D}_i \mathbf{f}_i^{ext}$$

- **Fibres-matrix Interface is represented by triangular prism elements (connecting faces of adjacent tetrahedra) with zero initial thickness.**

- **Interface elements can be used to model**
 - **Relative normal displacements leading to separation or de-bonding.**
 - **Relative tangential displacement or slip.**

- ❑ Matrix as isotropic material
(2 elastic constants) E, ν
- ❑ Fibres as transversely isotropic material
(5 elastic constants) $E_p, \nu_p, E_z, \nu_{pz}, G_{pz}$

- ❑ Rotation of stiffness matrix

$$C^* = T_\sigma C T_\epsilon^{-1}$$

Material parameters (E_s and G are in Gpa)

Fibres properties					Matrix Properties	
E_p	E_z	ν_p	ν_z	G_{pz}	E	ν
40	270	0.26	0.26	24	3.5	0.35

Geometry parameters (mm)

Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values
W_{warp}	0.3	W_{weft}	0.3
H_{warp}	0.1514	H_{weft}	0.0757
$h_{gap\ warp}$	0.09	$h_{gap\ weft}$	1.2
L_{RVE}	3.0	ν_{gap}	0.012
W_{RVE}	0.8		
H_{RVE}	0.3		

Elliptical cross sections and cubic splines paths.

□ Stress-strain diagram between macro-strain and homogenised stress

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{yy} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{yz} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{zx} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \text{Specified} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}$$

T. W. Chua. Multi-scale modeling of textile composites. Master's thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Technische Universiteit Eindhoven, January 2011.

- Comparison of macro-strain and homogenised stress for crimp and (0°/90°) non-crimp RVE

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{yy} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{yz} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{zx} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \text{Specified} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}$$

Comparison of macro-strain and homogenised stress for crimp and (0°/90°) non-crimp RVE

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□ The final calculated homogenized stiffness matrix is $\bar{\sigma} = C \bar{\epsilon}$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{xx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} & C_{15} & C_{16} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} & C_{25} & C_{26} \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & C_{34} & C_{35} & C_{36} \\ C_{41} & C_{42} & C_{43} & C_{44} & C_{45} & C_{46} \\ C_{51} & C_{52} & C_{53} & C_{54} & C_{55} & C_{56} \\ C_{61} & C_{62} & C_{63} & C_{64} & C_{65} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{yy} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{yz} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{zx} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}$$

- Relation between macro-strain and homogenized stress $\bar{\sigma} = C\bar{\epsilon}$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{xx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} & C_{15} & C_{16} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} & C_{25} & C_{26} \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & C_{34} & C_{35} & C_{36} \\ C_{41} & C_{42} & C_{43} & C_{44} & C_{45} & C_{46} \\ C_{51} & C_{52} & C_{53} & C_{54} & C_{55} & C_{56} \\ C_{61} & C_{62} & C_{63} & C_{64} & C_{65} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{yy} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{yz} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{zx} \\ 2\bar{\epsilon}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}$$

- First two columns of the stiffness matrix are written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{xx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} & C_{15} & C_{16} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} & C_{25} & C_{26} \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & C_{34} & C_{35} & C_{36} \\ C_{41} & C_{42} & C_{43} & C_{44} & C_{45} & C_{46} \\ C_{51} & C_{52} & C_{53} & C_{54} & C_{55} & C_{56} \\ C_{61} & C_{62} & C_{63} & C_{64} & C_{65} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} C_{11} \\ C_{21} \\ C_{31} \\ C_{41} \\ C_{51} \\ C_{61} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{xx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} & C_{15} & C_{16} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} & C_{25} & C_{26} \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & C_{34} & C_{35} & C_{36} \\ C_{41} & C_{42} & C_{43} & C_{44} & C_{45} & C_{46} \\ C_{51} & C_{52} & C_{53} & C_{54} & C_{55} & C_{56} \\ C_{61} & C_{62} & C_{63} & C_{64} & C_{65} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} C_{12} \\ C_{22} \\ C_{32} \\ C_{42} \\ C_{52} \\ C_{62} \end{Bmatrix}$$

- ❑ **An Initial computational multi-scale study to model the textile composite materials for the DURACOMP project.**
- ❑ **A single layered plain weave is used to model the textile geometry using CUBIT.**
- ❑ **Elliptical cross sections and cubic splines are used respectively to model the cross sections and paths of the fibre bundles.**
- ❑ **Transversely isotropic material is introduced for the fibre bundles, and elastic material is used for the matrix.**
- ❑ **The directions of the fibre bundles are calculated using a potential flow analysis across the fibre bundles**
- ❑ **Linear displacement boundary conditions and elastic interfaces between fibre bundles and matrix.**
- ❑ **RVE is analysed using the university of Glasgow in-house parallel computational tool, MoFEM (Mesh Oriented Finite Element Method).**

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